

Remapping of AWS data

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) is a new small weather satellite developed by OHB Sweden and the European Space Agency (ESA). The AWS was approved at the European Space Agency (ESA) Council meeting at Ministerial level in November 2019 as a new Earth Watch Programme Element, and is planned to be launched in 2024. AWS will provide measurements of atmospheric temperature and humidity and is seen as a prototype for a future constellation of microwave sounding satellites to support global and regional Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and nowcasting at high latitudes. EUMETSAT has now started defining such a constellation under the EPS-Sterna Programme.

AWS will be carrying a cross-track scanning microwave radiometer, operating in 19 channels covering a frequency range of 50 to 325 GHz. Each channel will provide data from about 145 field of views (FOVs) per scan, the footprint size of the samples around the nadir view will be about 8.5 – 40 km, and the swath width will be about 1800 km.

The AWS ground segment includes the Payload Data Ground Segment (PDGS). The PDGS is responsible for processing instrument source packets up to Level-1b, and distributing data to EUMETSAT's EUMETCast system, from where it will be distributed to end users. The Level-1b data includes the geolocation or a geodetic latitude and longitude associated to the center position of each FOV. The geolocation is calculated accounting for measured scan angles, the satellite position and attitude, pre-launch measurements of the antenna co-polar far-field pattern of the beam associated to each channel, and the instrument mounting on the satellite etc.

The four different receivers or feedhorns (associated to the channels operating around 50, 89, 183, and 325 GHz) will point in different directions at a given moment. The Level-1b processing of AWS data does not include a remapping of the AWS data, and hence data associated to a given channel are not necessarily co-located with data from a second channel. This is required for many applications.

1.2 Purpose of this document

This document describes the basis of an AWS Level-1C processor, that has been developed to allow for remapping of AWS data to a common grid. The Level-1C processor is based on the Backus-Gilbert footprint matching methodology, and this methodology, including an application on an early configuration of AWS, is described in [1]. The purpose of this document is to describe the application on the current and final configuration of AWS, including the basis and expected performance, while the usage and interface specifications of the actual Level-1C processor is described in the user manual associated to the processor.

1.3 Structure of this document

Section 2 gives an overview of reference coordinate systems and coordinate transformations that are relevant for the process of geolocating AWS samples on the ground. Section 3 describes AWS characteristics, and Section 4 covers the remapping of data.

2 Reference coordinate systems and coordinate transformations

2.1 Reference coordinate systems

2.1.1 Earth Centered Inertial (ECI) coordinate frame

ECI coordinate frames have their origins at the center of mass of Earth and do not rotate with respect to the stars. For objects in space, the equations of motion that describe orbital motion are simpler in a non-rotating frame. One commonly used ECI frame is defined with the Earth's Mean Equator and Equinox at 12:00 Terrestrial Time on 1 January 2000. It can be referred to as J2000 or EME2000. The x -axis is aligned with the mean equinox. The z -axis is aligned with the Earth's rotation axis or celestial North Pole. The y -axis is rotated by 90° East about the celestial equator.

2.1.2 Earth Centered Earth Fixed (ECEF) coordinate frame

ECEF coordinate frames remain fixed with respect to Earth's surface in its rotation. It represents positions as Cartesian x , y , and z coordinates. ECEF is referred to as a geocentric frame, the point $(0, 0, 0)$ is defined as the center of mass of Earth. The z -axis extends through the true north, which does not coincide with the instantaneous Earth rotational axis. The x -axis intersects the sphere of the earth at 0° latitude (the equator) and 0° longitude (prime meridian in Greenwich).

2.1.3 Geodetic reference system

A Geodetic reference system is a coordinate system, and a set of reference points, used for locating places on the Earth. In geodetic coordinates, the Earth's surface is approximated by an ellipsoid, and locations near the surface are described in terms of latitude, longitude, and altitude. An approximate definition of sea level is the datum WGS84. Geodetic latitude and geocentric latitude represent similar quantities with different definitions. Geodetic latitude is defined as the angle between the equatorial plane and the surface normal at a point on the ellipsoid, whereas geocentric latitude is defined as the angle between the equatorial plane and a radial line connecting the centre of the ellipsoid to a point on the surface. Geodetic altitude is defined as the height above the ellipsoid surface, normal to the ellipsoid, while a geocentric altitude is defined as the height above the ellipsoid surface along a line to the centre of the ellipsoid.

2.1.4 Orbital coordinate system (Orb)

The orbital coordinate system is centered on the satellite and its orientation is based on the spacecraft position in inertial space. The origin is the spacecraft center of mass with the z -axis pointing from the spacecraft center of mass to the direction perpendicular to the reference ellipsoid. The y -axis is the normalized cross product of the z -axis and the instantaneous (inertial) velocity vector. The x -axis is the cross product of the y and z axes.

2.1.5 Spacecraft coordinate system (SC)

The spacecraft coordinate system is fixed to the spacecraft with its origin at the spacecraft center of mass. The coordinate axes are defined by the spacecraft attitude control system. The x -, y -, and z -axis represent an orthogonal reference frame related to the satellite axes. Nominal attitude pointing consists of the best possible alignment of this set of axes with the Orbital coordinate system. It is the orientation of this coordinate system relative to the Orbital coordinate system that is captured in the spacecraft attitude data.

2.1.6 Sensor Head coordinate system (SH)

The sensor head coordinate system is the coordinate system in which a space vector emanating from the sensor is converted to a space viewing vector. The z -axis points towards zenith, and the positive x -axis is aligned with the along-track direction (direction of spacecraft motion), and the y -axis completes the orthogonal and right-hand coordinate system.

2.2 Coordinate transformations

2.2.1 ECI to ECEF

The transformation of coordinates back and forth between ECEF and ECI systems is in general non-trivial as this depends on Earth rotation, nutation, precession, and polar motion, and e.g. polar motion can not be predicted theoretically, but data to estimate these parameters can be obtained from International Earth Rotation and Reference Systems Service (IERS) bulletins. The ECI to ECEF rotation matrix can be expressed as a composite of transformations:

- $R_{ECEF/ECI} = R_A \cdot R_B \cdot R_C \cdot R_D$,
- R_A - polar motion,
- R_B - sidereal time,
- R_C - nutation,
- R_D - precession.

It is noted that the Astropy Project, that is a community effort to develop a common core package for astronomy in Python, provides a tool for transformation between these coordinate systems.

2.2.2 Orb to ECI

The relationship between the orbital and ECI coordinate systems is based on the spacecraft's instantaneous ECI position and velocity vectors. The rotation matrix to convert from orbital to ECI can be constructed by forming the orbital coordinate system axes in ECI coordinates as described below:

- $R_{ECI/Orb} = (\vec{u}_x \quad \vec{u}_y \quad \vec{u}_z)$,
- \vec{p} - spacecraft position vector (ECI),
- \vec{v} - spacecraft velocity vector (ECI),
- \vec{h} - geodetic nadir location vector on ellipsoid (ECI),
- $\vec{u}_z = -(\vec{p} - \vec{h})/|\vec{p} - \vec{h}|$,
- $\vec{u}_y = \vec{u}_z \times \vec{v}/|\vec{u}_z \times \vec{v}|$,
- $\vec{u}_x = \vec{u}_y \times \vec{u}_z$,

where \times is the cross product and $||$ denotes the l^2 -norm.

2.2.3 SC to Orb

The relationship between the spacecraft and orbital coordinate systems is defined by the spacecraft attitude. The transformation from spacecraft to orbital coordinates is a three-dimensional rotation matrix with the components of the rotation matrix being functions of the spacecraft yaw(α), pitch(β), and roll (γ) attitude angle. This transformation is time varying, since the spacecraft attitude is constantly changing:

- $R_{Orb/SC}(t) = R_z(\alpha) \cdot R_y(\beta) \cdot R_x(\gamma)$

- $R_z = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\alpha) & -\sin(\alpha) & 0 \\ \sin(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$

- $R_y = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\beta) & 0 & \sin(\beta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\beta) & 0 & \cos(\beta) \end{pmatrix}$

- $R_x = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\gamma) & -\sin(\gamma) \\ 0 & \sin(\gamma) & \cos(\gamma) \end{pmatrix}$

2.2.4 SH to SC

The sensor head alignment matrix describes the relationship between the instrument and the spacecraft coordinate systems. The nominal rotation matrix for a perfectly aligned instrument is:

- $R_{SC/SH} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

3 The Arctic Weather Satellite

3.1 Overview

AWS is planned to operate in a sun-synchronous low Earth orbit (LEO), with an altitude of approximately 600 km, an inclination of 97.8°, an orbital period of 97 minutes, and a repeat cycle of three days. AWS is carrying a cross-track scanning microwave radiometer (MWR). MWR consists of a rotating (50 rpm) antenna, which focuses incoming radiation onto one of four feedhorns and four receivers. Each of the feedhorns is directed towards a slightly different point on ground, and data from in total 19 channels covering a frequency range of 50–325 GHz are acquired. Each channel will provide samples from about 145 FOVs for each scan, the footprint size of the samples around the nadir view will be about 8.5–40 km, and the swath width will be about 1800 km.

3.2 Channel description

Table 1: Specification of MWR channels. NE Δ T values represent measured and required (in parenthesis) ones. Reported footprint size refers to the nadir view.

Channel	Centre Freq. [GHz]	Bandwidth [MHz]	NE Δ T [K]	Footprint size [km]
11	50.3	180	0.484 (0.9)	≤ 40
12	52.8	400	0.363 (0.7)	
13	53.246	300	0.396 (0.4)	
14	53.596	370	0.354 (0.7)	
15	54.4	400	0.365 (0.7)	
16	54.94	400	0.412 (0.7)	
17	55.5	330	0.515 (0.7)	
18	57.290344	330	1.181 (0.75)	
21	89.0	4000	0.21 (0.5)	≤ 20
31	165.5	2800	0.363 (0.6)	≤ 10
32	176.311	2000	0.499 (0.8)	
33	178.811	2000	0.561 (0.8)	
34	180.311	1000	0.787 (1.0)	
35	181.511	1000	0.839 (1.0)	
36	182.311	500	0.996 (1.3)	
41	325.15 \pm 1.2	2 * 800	1.601 (1.7)	
42	325.15 \pm 2.4	2 * 1200	1.532 (1.4)	
43	325.15 \pm 4.1	2 * 1800	1.051 (1.2)	
44	325.15 \pm 6.6	2 * 2800	0.908 (1.0)	

3.3 Pointing description

The scanning involves two rotations, and Figure 1 describes how the pointing direction of the effectively four beams of MWR can be modelled in an idealised way. The two rotations are most naturally described in the sensor head (SH) and the antenna or beam (B) reference coordinate systems, where (for a nominal attitude of the S/C):

- x_{sh} -axis is aligned with the nose of the S/C or with the along-track direction,
- z_{sh} -axis points in the zenith direction,
- y_{sh} -axis is orthogonal to the x_{sh} -axis and z_{sh} -axis,
- x_b -axis is aligned with the x_{sh} -axis,
- y_b -axis and z_b -axis are located in the plane spanned up the y_{sh} -axis and z_{sh} -axis.

Figure 1: High level description of the AWS/MWR scanning geometry in the sensor head (SH) and beam or antenna (B) reference coordinate systems. The colored arrows represent boresight direction vectors of the beams associated to each of the four feedhorns, ($\theta_i=6.12^\circ$ at 54 GHz , $\theta_i=3.04^\circ$ at 89 GHz , $\theta_i=1.35^\circ$ at 183 GHz , and $\theta_i=2.63^\circ$ at 325 GHz). See text for more details.

The scanning involves one rotation around the x_{sh} -axis that effectively gives the cross-track scanning, and a second rotation of the antenna around the z_b -axis, both with a speed of about 50 rpm, and these rotations are continuous (360° / scan). A direction vector in the SH coordinate system, $\vec{r}_{SH,i}$, representing the pointing of the beam associated to channel i , can be described by:

$$\vec{r}_{SH,i}(t) = R_{SH/B}(t) \cdot \vec{r}_{B,i}(t) = R_x(-\theta(t)) \cdot \vec{r}_{B,i}(t), \quad (1)$$

where t is time, R_x represents a basic rotation matrix around the x -axis, θ is a scan angle that can be described by

$$\theta(t) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot t / \Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where Δt is the scan duration (1.191 s), and $\vec{r}_{B,i}$ represents the direction vector of the beam in the B coordinate system that can be described by

$$\vec{r}_{B,i}(t) = [\sin(\theta_i) \cdot \cos(\vartheta_i(t)) \quad \sin(\theta_i) \cdot \sin(\vartheta_i(t)) \quad \cos(\theta_i)]^T \quad (3)$$

where

$$\vartheta_i(t) = \vartheta_i^0 - 2 \cdot \pi \cdot t / \Delta t \quad (4)$$

and the two angles ϑ_i^0 and θ_i have fixed and well known values, but the values are channel, or actually feedhorn or band (e.g. apply to all channels operating within V band), specific.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the spacecraft (SC) and sensor head (SH) coordinate system. X_{SC} , Y_{SC} , and Z_{SC} are the axes of the SC coordinate system, and X_{SH} , Y_{SH} , and Z_{SH} are the axes of the SH or instrument coordinate system. Z_{SC} is pointing towards the nadir direction and C indicates the point of intersection with the Earth surface. r_{SC} and r'_{SC} represent a perfect and perturbed beam direction vector, respectively, and point A and B represent the positions of the beams intersection with the Earth surface

3.3.1 Scan pattern on ground

The geolocation of the intersection of the beam direction vector and the Earth surface involves the transformation of the beam vector to an ECEF (Earth-centered, Earth-fixed) coordinate system, that can be achieved by:

$$\vec{r}_{ECEF} = R_{ECEF/ECI} \cdot R_{ECI/Orb} \cdot R_{Orb/SC} \cdot R_{SC/SH} \cdot R_{SH/B} \cdot \vec{r}_B, \quad (5)$$

where $R_{A/B}$ represents a rotation matrix that can transform a direction vector from coordinate system A to B (and its transpose from B to A). Involved reference coordinate systems and rotation matrixes are described in Section 2. Given the satellite position \vec{p}_{ECEF} and \vec{r}_{ECEF} the intersection with Earth surface can be obtained from a geometry calculation. Figure 3 describes the pattern of AWS scan lines at the surface. The rotation of the antenna effectively gives that the swath width varies a bit with channel.

Figure 3: The center position of each sample on the geoid for two complete scans of AWS, where the second scan is three scans ahead of the first one. The S/C is flying towards north, and the scanning direction is then towards east. It is assumed that AWS provides 145 samples per channel and scan, between scanning angles of about $\pm 55^\circ$ around nadir. The sub-satellite path during the two scans are shown with black dots. The centre scan position (73), or the position where the antenna pointing vector (Z_b in Figure 1) points towards nadir, is shown with a bigger marker for each scan line and channel, and it can be seen that this scan position does necessarily correspond to the most nadir view for the channels.

3.4 Footprint description

Figure 4 shows -20 dB footprints associated to four AWS channels at five positions of a given scan. These footprints are based on a quasi-optics simulation [2] of the farfield beam. A smoothing of the co-polar farfield beam to compensate for the beam rotation and movement in the across-track direction during the 2.5 ms sample integration time is applied, following a methodology described in [1]. It is assumed that the rotation of the beam around the pointing vector is in the anti-clockwise direction, and rotates $360^\circ / \text{scan}$. The more detailed beam pattern projected on the ground is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: -20 dB footprints, for five scan positions (30, 50, 73, 96, 116) and for four of the AWS channels and for one of the scan shown in Figure 3.

Figure 5: The co-polar farfield, associated to the ASW-11, AWS-21, AWS-31, and AWS-41 channel, (from top to bottom panel) projected onto ground for five scan positions (30, 50, 73, 96, 116), for one of the scan described in Figure 3. The -20 dB contours displayed in Figure 4 are shown also here.

4 Remapping of AWS data

4.1 Aim

The Backus-Gilbert (BG) footprint matching methodology, described in more details in [1], is applied for the remapping of AWS data. In short, the BG methodology can be used to obtain a set of optimal weighting coefficients for neighbouring samples, both within the scan and from adjacent scans, to create a remapped representation of the data matching a specified target footprint. A remapped value is a linearly weighted combination of data of the channel of concern. The weights are found, after a trade-off analysis, by minimisation of a penalty function that considers both the effective noise of the remapped data and the fit to the target footprint.

Thus, the BG methodology is a powerful method and can in theory be used to remap data onto any type of target grid and footprint pattern shape. In practise, only a few type of remappings are of interest. The one selected and explored here is the remapping of data to match the geolocation of that of the samples associated to 183 GHz channel(s), and to keep the native spatial resolution of the data (Figure 6), as this was the most desirable one according to end-users.

Figure 6: The upper panel shows native -3 dB footprints, for five scan positions (30, 50, 73, 96, 116) and for four of the AWS channels and for one of the scan shown in Figure 3. The lower panel shows the aim of the remapping primarily considered here, i.e. to remap the data to match the center position of the samples associated to the AWS-31 channel, but keeping the native resolution of the data. The remapping target is constructed from an imagined beam of the feedhorn associated to the AWS-31 channel, e.g. by using the farfield beam associated to the AWS-11 channel for data associated to the AWS-11 channel.

4.2 Derivation of optimal weighting coefficients

4.2.1 Algorithm and setup

Figure 7 depicts a schematic of the algorithm used for obtaining optimal weighting coefficients, and the algorithm can be summarised by:

- calculate the center position on the geoid associated to the target footprint,
- generate a rectangular grid, of suitable size and resolution, with grid points located on the geoid and centered around the center of the target footprint, and with an orientation that is aligned with the across-track scan direction,
- identify all samples (associated to the channel that is to be remapped) that have a geolocation close to the center of the target footprint,
- project the farfield beam associated to the target observation and all involved samples on each facet (flat surface between grid points) off the grid,
- apply the Backus-Gilbert methodology and make a trade off analysis in order to get weights that gives best possible characteristic of the reconstructed observation.

The grid is generated in a parameterised way and is made wide enough to cover an off boresight viewing angle off 10° w.r.t. the viewing direction of the target sample. The resolution of the grid is made fine enough to match the resolution of the native farfield beam data described in Sect. 3.4. This corresponds to 0.05° or about 500 m on the geoid for a close to nadir viewing target footprint.

All samples that are found within a polar angle θ_{max} relative to the boresight direction of the target observation are here included for the calculation related to the remapping of data onto a given FOV (see upper left panel of Figure 7). A value of $\theta_{max} = 1.64^\circ$ is used here, and this gives that samples associated to about four to five scan lines and scan positions will be included in the calculation. This was found to be enough for the type of remapping considered here.

The Backus-Gilbert application includes an optimization, or a trade off between fit error and noise (low fit-error generally gives high noise level and vice verse). Optimal weights are obtained from an "L-curve" plot where the curvature is greatest (see Sect. 3.2 and Figure 5 in [1]), considering a range of values of a smoothing parameter β , and here values within the range 10^{-7} to 10^{-4} are used.

4.2.2 Individual examples

Figure 7 to 9 show examples of remapping weights derived for the remapping of data associated to the 89 GHz , 325 GHz , and 54 GHz channel onto the view associated to the 183 GHz channel for scan position 115 of a given scan. It can clearly be seen that the fit to target is better for the data associated to 54 GHz and 89 GHz channel compared to the the data associated to the 325 GHz channel, as the target footprint is less oversampled in the latter case. It can also be noted the remapping of data will introduce a small geolocation error, even if such an error is not present in the native data.

Figure 7: Schematic for the remapping of samples associated to the 89 GHz channel onto the view associated to the 183 GHz channel for scan position 115. The upper left panel shows the remapping target pattern (i.e. the co-polar farfield pattern associated to the 89 GHz channel as seen from the view of the 183 GHz channel, and the red line represent the -20 dB footprint). The red star indicates the center position of the target footprint. The orange circles represent the center position of neighbouring 89 GHz samples. The upper right panel shows the half power footprints of the 89 GHz samples, together with the the target footprint (red) and the footprint obtained from the remapped data (magenta). The geolocation error of the obtained footprint is 30 m . The lower left panel shows the derived optimal weights to apply for the remapping and based on the Backus-Gilbert footprint methodology. The remapped value can be obtained from a linear combination of the weights and the associated brightness temperatures, and the remapped pattern on ground as a linear combination of the weights and the associated projected farfield of the involved samples. The lower right panel shows target and obtained pattern in the along and across track direction. These are hard to distinguish from each other as they more or less lie on top of each other.

Figure 8: As Figure 7, but for the remapping of samples associated to the 325 GHz channel onto the view associated to the 183 GHz channel for scan position 115.

Figure 9: As Figure 7, but for the remapping of samples associated to the 50 GHz channel onto the view associated to the 183 GHz channel for scan position 115.

4.2.3 Scan position and platform altitude dependent performance

Figure 10 describes the performance of the remapping of data onto the center position of each footprint associated to the 183 GHz channel and for four scanlines with an associated platform altitude of 605, 615, 625, and 635 km . It can clearly be seen that the remapping performance (and optimal weights) varies a bit with platform altitude, and needs to be taken into account by an operational remapping.

The remapping generally works well except for scan position number above ~ 140 and for the 50 (AWS11) and 325 (ASW41) GHz data, where the fit-error is high as expected due to coverage problem (see Figure 3). Except for this, the remapping of the 50 GHz data provides the smallest fit-error, as the footprints and oversampling are greater for this channel compared to the other channels. The fit-error varies with scan position, particularly for the 89 and 325 GHz data. A "local minimum error" is obtained when one of the native sample is located close to the target, and as e.g. several "89 GHz scanlines" crosses a single "183 GHz scanline" this results in a wave-like fit-error pattern.

It can further be seen that the remapping of data effectively reduces $NE\Delta T$ compared to that of the native samples, and the best reduction ($\sim 50\%$) is seen for data associated to the 50 GHz channel, and for data associated to the 89 and 325 GHz channels the reduction is in the range of 0 to 40 % and 0 to 30 %, respectively. The noise is reduced as the remapped data represents an average of many samples, and this can also be seen in the third panel that displays the maximum weight associated to one of the sample to utilize, and this value is most often smaller than one. For some scan positions the value is close to one, and this indicates that one of the available native sample is close to perfectly geolocated with the target footprint.

A fixed value of $\beta = 10^{-6}$ was applied for the smoothing parameter used for the optimization covering the 50 GHz data. This is due to the fact that the optimization (trade-off between noise and fit-error) provides a less pronounced optimum than for the 89 and 325 GHz data, where an actual optimization were done.

Figure 10: The performance of the remapping of data onto the center position of each footprint associated to the 183 GHz channel and for four scanlines with an associated platform altitude of 605, 615, 625, and 635 km . The upper panel displays assumed $\text{NE}\Delta\text{T}$ value associated to native samples in dashed lines and that of the remapped data in solid lines. The second panel displays the fit error of the remapped data, the third panel the maximum weight associated to a single sample, and the lowermost panel shows the value of the smoothing parameter (β).

4.2.4 Sensitivity analysis

The remapping of AWS is clearly sensitive to any type of geolocation error in the native data, as such an error will be transferred to the remapped data. However, it is not the task of the remapping to correct for a geolocation error, and we do not cover such an error here. The remapping of data can on the other hand introduce a geolocation error even if such an error is not present in the native data. We here assess the sensitivity of the remapping performance to using non-optimal weighting coefficients.

Figure 11 shows the effect of applying the weighting coefficients derived for the remapping of data for a neighbouring scan position. This would correspond to a situation where the actual AWS scan starts a bit later (one scan position) than expected but not taking into account of this in the remapping calculation. It can be seen that this clearly results in a greater fit and geolocation error compared to using the optimal weights as done in Figure 7. The geolocation error introduced by the non-optimal remapping is 0.87 km in this case. It was found (but not shown) that the remapping of data associated to the 50 GHz channel is most sensitive to this type of error, with a geolocation error of 1.91 km for the corresponding test. The reason for this can be explained by the fact that the " 50 GHz scan line" is less parallel to the " 183 GHz scan line" than what the " 89 GHz scan line" is, and consequently the weighting coefficients effectively vary more rapidly with scan position for the " 50 GHz case".

Optimal weighting coefficients are not only channel and scan position dependent, but also depends on the platform altitude even if the scanning is perfectly cyclic, and the platform altitude will not be constant but vary by about 40 km within one given orbit (altitude is smallest around the equator). A sensitivity test to platform altitude showed that if the difference between the actual and assumed orbit altitude is above 5 km , this can result in a geolocation error above 1 km in the remapped data.

The magnitude of the geolocation error introduced by non-optimal remapping in the examples described above is certainly not desirable, but still smaller than the geolocation accuracy requirement of AWS Level-1b data (2 km around nadir view) and should therefore not be very severe.

It is recognized that deviations from the nominal AWS operation will have an impact on the remapping performance if not taking into account, but by taking it into account by using a matching set of weighting coefficients for the current situation the resulting error can be small compared to the geolocation accuracy requirement of Level-1B data.

Figure 11: As Figure 7 (remapping of 89 GHz data), but using weighting coefficients derived for the remapping of data for a neighbouring scan position (114) for scan position 115.

4.3 Operational remapping

Generally, optimal weighting coefficients will be specific for each single remapping. However, the derivation of optimal weighting coefficients is a rather computational costly task, and considered to be too costly to be derived on the fly for an operational Level-1c processor, as a good timeliness of the data is a critical aspect for many end-users / applications. The AWS Level-1c processor utilizes a set of pre-calculated remapping weighting coefficients, and only performs the remapping of AWS data through a convolution operation, using a pre-computed convolution matrix/filter kernel. The pre-computed convolution matrix has been generated to cover the type of remapping described in Sect. 4.1 and optimal weights have been derived for each scan position of a number of scans with a varying platform altitude (see Figure 10).

The remapping for a given scan position (x), scan number (y), and channel (k) can then be achieved through a convolution operation:

$$T_r(x, y, k) = \omega * T_b(x, y, k) = \sum_{i=-a_1}^{a_2} \sum_{j=-b_1}^{b_2} \omega(x, y, k, i, j) T_b(x + i, y + j, k), \quad (6)$$

where T_b and T_r denotes calibrated brightness temperature associated to the native samples and remapped data, respectively, ω denotes the weight or convolution matrix/filter kernel.

It is noted that the remapping algorithm aims for using the set of pre-calculated weights that best matches the conditions of the actual measurement, that is, with respect to platform altitude and centering of the scan around the nadir view (i.e. handling of non nominal scans). Input to the AWS Level-1c processor is AWS Level-1B data and the *satellite altitude* and *aws satellite zenith angle* quantities of the *navigation* dataset are used for finding best weights for a given case.

Figure 12 shows that data from about 30 scans, corresponding to an observation sequence of about 36 s, is needed for the remapping of data onto center position of each FOV of a given scan. The remapping of data will not perfectly cover the full swath of the first 10 and last 20 scans of the input Level-1B data due to that data from scan lines outside the current dataset are needed for this. It is noted that related data coverage gaps can be avoided by concatenating adjacent Level-1B datasets, although this can be impossible for near real time processing of data as the needed data might not yet be available.

Figure 12: Relative scan numbers as function of scan position from which data are utilized for the remapping of data onto center position of fofs of AWS31 data for a given scan. Data are shown for AWS11, AWS21, and AWS41 data.

4.3.1 Expected performance

The processing time for remapping of AWS data covering one orbit, by applying a set of precalculated weighting coefficients, is expected to be about 10 to 20 *s* using a standard machine.

The type of remapping described in Section 4.1 is expected to work well for scan position number 1 to 140, but for the outermost scan positions (i.e. 141 to 145) some of the channels lack coverage with respect to the coverage of data associated to the 183 GHz channel (see Figure 3), and the remapping of data will not perfectly cover the full swath of the first 10 and last 20 scans (see Figure 12).

The geolocation error introduced by the remapping of data is expected to be negligible small (well below 1 *km*) compared to the geolocation accuracy requirement of AWS level-1B data, as long as AWS operates in a close to nominal mode.

The remapping of data will effectively reduce $NE\Delta T$ compared to that of the native samples, and the best reduction ($\sim 50\%$) is expected for data associated to channels around 50 *GHz*, and for data associated to the 89 and 325 *GHz* channels the reduction is in the range of 0 to 40 % and 0 to 30 %, respectively, in both cases varying with scan position (see Figure 10).

4.3.2 Remapping bias

It is noted that the type of remapping of data considered here only aims for matching target footprints on ground, and does not aim to correct for the fact that the associated incidence angle of the constructed target footprint may differ from the effective incidence angle of remapped data. Incidence angle differences are displayed in Figure 13, and it can be seen that the difference is below 1° for the main part of the scan except around the center part of the scan where a difference above 2° can be seen. In practise this means that the remapped data will be biased compared to an imaginary perfect sample, as the observed brightness temperature depends on incidence angle as described in more detail in Figure 16 in [1]. Fortunately, the effect is weak for low incidence angles and the main issue should be in the outer part of the scan and for data associated to channels around 50 *GHz* where an incidence angle difference of 1° can or should result in a bias of about 1 *K* if not taking into account. This type of error is expected to be less severe for data associated to other channels as the incidence angle difference is below about 0.5° . A direct bias correction of the remapped data taking the incidence angle difference issue into account is a challenging task, as the resulting bias is state dependent. For a retrieval application based on AWS data, it can be taking into account by applying the effective incidence angle associated to the remapped data in the calculation.

Figure 13: The upper panel shows the incidence angle (satellite zenith angle), associated to the target (AWS31) footprint, as function of scan position. The bottom panel shows the difference in incidence angle associated to the sample given the highest weight in the remapping calculation to that of the target footprint, for the other channels.

5 References

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